
Comparative Assessment of Soil Water Retention and Porosity in Leguminous and Non-Leguminous Cropping Systems

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ABSTRACT: Crop yield and soil physical condition depend heavily on soil water retention and porosity. This study examined the effects of leguminous (soybean and pea) and non-leguminous (sunflower and maize) cropping systems on selected indicators. 24 undisturbed samples were collected from the 0-7.5 cm depth of West Farm, Murray, Kentucky. They were used to determine bulk density, porosity, soil water holding capacity (SWHC), and soil water field capacity (SWFC). Results showed Sunflower had the highest SWHC (29.13%) and SWFC (24.32%). Peas, on the other hand, had the lowest SWHC (25.29%) and SWFC (19.92%). The bulk density was higher in legumes (soybean: 1.72 g cm⁻³; peas: 1.73 g cm⁻³) than for non-legumes (sunflower: 1.69 g cm⁻³; maize: 1.66 g cm⁻³). Similar trends were observed in macroporosity, with peas exhibiting the lowest percentage (24.22%) and sunflowers showing the highest (28.05%). Peas had the highest microporosity (10.35%); however, this did not translate into a larger SWFC, indicating that water retention is controlled by the total pore distribution rather than microporosity alone. A similar pattern was observed in total porosity, with peas showing the lowest value (34.57%) and maize the highest (37.23%). Overall, the results show that non-leguminous crops outperformed leguminous crops across key soil water retention metrics. Their better water retention and porosity imply that biomass inputs and root designs improve soil physical structure more effectively than legumes do. These results highlight the importance of crop selection in improving soil hydraulic properties and the need to employ a range of cropping techniques to sustain soil health.

KEY WORDS: Cropping systems, legumes, Porosity, Soil water retention

INTRODUCTION

Plant development, nutrient delivery, and general soil function all depend heavily on soil water retention. The distribution of pore sizes, especially the ratio of micropores that store water to macropores that aid in drainage and aeration, significantly influences the soil's capacity to hold and deliver water. Two commonly used metrics to measure soil water availability are soil water holding capacity (SWHC) and soil water at field capacity (SWFC) (Tuller et al., 2004).

Legumes help increase soil organic matter, which improves the soil's ability to retain water. Leguminous plants release organic substances through root exudates into the soil. By increasing aggregation and stability, these substances improve soil structure by acting as binding agents. They can increase porosity by lowering bulk density. Aeration and root growth depend on this. Water and air may pass through soil more easily due to increased porosity (Chen et al., 2018). Legumes have a positive effect on several water-related processes, including reducing erosion and runoff. Water is more available due to improved soil structure and increased organic matter content, which also increases water infiltration and water-holding capacity. These crops' root systems and residues help form soil aggregates, improving soil porosity, aeration, and water flow. Thus, the soil's total physical composition improves (Liang et al., 2010).

Several non-leguminous crops have the capacity to directly boost nutrient availability through root exudates or indirectly through symbiotic connections with certain soil bacteria (Camargo et al., 2023), whereas leguminous crops increase N availability through N-fixation. For instance, some cereal grains, such as maize and barley, release phyto siderophores in their root exudates to solubilize Fe(III) or organic acids to mobilize and improve the availability of P that is not accessible to plants (Marschner et al., 2011).

Weather patterns are already being affected by climate change, increasing the risk of farming because drought and flooding expose soil to erosion and deterioration. Long stretches of dryness will follow heavy, rapid rainfall, and traditional production agriculture's soils are unable to adapt to the changing climate. Therefore, a high soil water-holding capacity is crucial for mitigating the effects of climate change (Borisova et al., 2009). Precise geographic assessment of root-zone accessible Soil water holding capacity

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(SWHC) and Soil water field capacity (SWFC) can improve site-specific management techniques, including variable-rate irrigation, to reduce input costs, decrease pollutant leaching, and/or increase crop production. A field estimate of Field Capacity can be obtained by measuring the volumetric water content when wet soils drain after significant precipitation (Lo et al., 2017).

The amount, size distribution, and connection of soil porosity regulate the flow of gas and water through microbial communities and soils, connecting hydrological and biogeochemical cycles. The United Nations SDG 15.3.1, for instance, uses soil carbon stocks as an indicator of land degradation (Sims et al., 2020). In contrast, bulk density (BD), which characterizes the quantity of soil solids per unit volume, is necessary to quantify soil carbon and nutrient stocks. One of the globally recognized soil hazards affecting plant development and biogeochemical cycling is changes in soil porosity induced by compaction (Fatichi et al., 2020). An essential component of soil quality research is the assessment of soil pore space. The formation and growth of pores, whose characteristics significantly impact soil behavior, are driven by the mobility of the soil's solid, liquid, and gas components. Soil aggregates and other soil characteristics are correlated with the distribution of soil pore sizes. Subdivisions of soil pores can reveal more specific characteristics of the soil under investigation. Based on their size, pores can be categorized as micropores, mesopores, or macropores. Changes in soil processes, whether man-made or natural, can result in the formation or destruction of pores as well as modifications to their size and other characteristics (Nimmo, 2004).

While non-leguminous crops, particularly cereals and broadleaf species, contribute significant biomass and deeper rooting patterns that affect porosity and aggregation, leguminous crops frequently improve soil structure through increased microbial activity and nitrogen fixation. Comparative evaluations of soil hydraulic characteristics between leguminous and non-leguminous systems remain few, despite these established impacts. This study aims to provide a quantitative comparison of soil water retention and porosity indicators across four common crops-Soybean, peas, sunflower, and maize -representing two contrasting cropping systems.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. Soil water retention concepts

The amount of water on a mass or volume basis that remains in soil two or three days after the soil has been wetted with water and after free drainage is minimal is known as the Soil water field water capacity (SFWC). After all soil macropores have been emptied and refilled with air, it is the maximum amount of water that a soil can retain against gravity (Lal & Shukla, 2004). The ability of soil to retain water at a specific time of year is known as soil water-holding capacity (SWHC; Olorunfemi et al., 2016). The boundary between infiltration, runoff, and evaporation occurs at the soil's surface. Under specific climatic conditions, the relative intensity of each component of this partitioning—that is, how much rain will infiltrate and possibly be intercepted by plant roots or drain toward groundwater, how much will flow as runoff, or how much will evaporate back to the atmosphere—will be determined by the soil properties of the upper soil layer like Soil water holding capacity and soil water field capacity. Some of its primary hydrological and agricultural activities, including infiltration and evaporation capacity, time to ponding, drainage toward field capacity, length of stage-1 evaporation, and accessible water for plant uptake, are determined by the characteristics of the topsoil layer. When designing effective irrigation systems or forecasting flood disasters, several of these characteristics are crucial components. Therefore, to forecast hydrological response or agricultural potential, it is crucial to estimate these soil functions a priori using readily available, easily measurable parameters (Assouline, 2021). Because it governs most of the engineering behavior of soil, soil water retention characteristics (SWRC) are crucial for soil in agricultural fields as well as in geotechnical or geoenvironmental engineering structures such as bioengineered slopes and embankments, green roofs, and landfill cover. SWRC is the correlation between water content and soil suction (Hussain et al., 2020).

3.2 Effects of leguminous crops on soil health.

The Fabaceae family of plants includes legumes, which are unique in that they can add nitrogen to the soil through a process known as biological nitrogen fixation. Legumes form partnerships with nitrogen-fixing bacteria in their roots to increase soil fertility and produce seeds in pods. According to Jensen et al. (2012), legume-based systems have improved soil physicochemical and biological characteristics. Additionally, Ngangom et al. (2017) found that adding legumes to a maize-based cropping system significantly improved soil physical, chemical, and biological characteristics as well as maize equivalent production. Legumes have a beneficial effect on several water-related processes, including reducing erosion and runoff. Improved soil structure and organic matter content give plants better access to water, increasing water penetration rates and water-holding capacity. By covering the soil's surface and lowering leaching and nutrient runoff, they help prevent the loss of plant nutrients. Furthermore, these crops' dense cover serves as a barrier against erosion, preventing topsoil from being washed away. By encouraging soil aggregation, leguminous cover crops affect soil structure. These crops' root systems and residues help form soil aggregates, improving soil porosity, aeration, and water flow. As a result, the soil's overall physical condition improves (Meena, 2017).

3.3 Effect of non-leguminous crops on soil health

Any plant that neither forms root nodules with nitrogen-fixing bacteria nor fixes nitrogen from the atmosphere is considered a non-legume. A non-legume crop requires fertilizers or soil nutrients to grow, as it cannot naturally supply nitrogen to the soil. Numerous

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non-legume plants can fix nitrogen through endogenous or exogenous symbiosis with N₂-fixing organisms. Certain commercially significant cereal crops, such as rice, wheat, maize, and millets, have been linked to microbes that can fix atmospheric nitrogen (Saikia & Jain, 2007).

3.4 Pore size distribution and Soil functions

The distribution of soil pore sizes significantly influences water retention, hydraulic conductivity, gas exchange, and root growth. Based on size, soil pores can be classified as macropores, mesopores, or micropores, each with a unique ecological and hydrological role. Plant water availability and aeration are directly affected by the overall balance among different pore classes, which also determines the soil's physical health (Brady & Weil, 2016). The main functions of macropores (>0.08 mm diameter) are to control soil aeration, drainage, and water infiltration. Biological processes such as root penetration, soil fauna migration, and aggregation processes frequently produce these holes. After irrigation or rainfall, well-developed macropores enable excess water to drain quickly, avoiding waterlogging and promoting root respiration (Jarvis, 2020). Through constant root turnover and bioturbation, cropping systems with deep or fibrous roots often promote macropore development. On the other hand, water is held in place against gravity by micropores (less than 0.03 mm in diameter). During dry spells, water retained in micropores is the main source of plant-available water and significantly increases the soil's capacity to keep water (Hillel, 2003). But too much microporosity might impede root development and microbial activity by limiting airflow and creating anaerobic conditions (Brady & Weil, 2016). Total porosity, which is inversely correlated with bulk density, is the total volume of all the pore spaces in a soil matrix. In general, a soil with a high total porosity has higher root penetration, increased infiltration capacity, and better water storage. However, the size distribution and connectedness of pores have a greater impact on soil water behavior than pore volume alone (Kutilek & Nielsen, 2001). Therefore, sustaining effective water circulation, aeration, and storage within soil systems requires an ideal balance between macropores and micropores. Soil hydraulic performance may be significantly affected by cropping systems that alter bulk density, organic matter levels, and biological activity (Bronick & Lal, 2005). Therefore, building sustainable cropping systems that improve soil water-use efficiency and physical resilience requires an understanding of pore dynamics.

3.5 Influence of Bulk Density

According to Martínez et al. (2017), Bulk density (ρ_b) is a crucial soil physical feature used as an input parameter for water and nutrient transport models and is required to determine soil water characteristics. To get accurate estimates of soil organic carbon (OC) stocks using weight-to-volume conversions, bulk density must be evaluated accurately. The bulk density values are influenced by a variety of parameters, including compaction, organic matter concentration, and depth. In general, variations in particle size distribution (PSD) are the main cause of variations in bulk density values among soils. The most used metrics for describing the compactness of a soil layer are total porosity and dry bulk density. Finding a criterion for characterizing compactness that yields directly comparable values across all soils is necessary, as compactness is a crucial aspect of soil structure and quality. For this, a relative bulk density value—specifically, the degree of compactness—is used (Håkansson & Lipiec, 2000).

3.6 Research gaps

The physical characteristics of soil under various cropping systems have been well studied in the past, including how legumes can improve soil fertility through microbial improvement and biological nitrogen fixation (Neves et al., 2022). Additionally, several studies have found that soil organic carbon, aggregation, and texture significantly affect soil water retention (Herawati et al., 2021). However, rather than offering a thorough evaluation of soil hydrophysical characteristics across various cropping systems, most previous research has either focused on chemical soil properties or long-term production outcomes. Most research evaluates soil water retention separately, without including structural markers such as bulk density and total porosity in the analysis (Panagea et al., 2021). This limits our understanding of the simultaneous interactions among soil compaction, pore distribution, and pore connectivity that affect field water availability. Furthermore, there are still a few crop-specific comparison analyses in the literature, especially for crops such as soybeans, pea, maize, and sunflower. The integrated assessment of soil water retention and porosity in both leguminous and non-leguminous agricultural systems clearly have a study deficit. Understanding crop-specific effects on soil physical health and creating sustainable agricultural systems that maximize soil water resources in the face of changing climate conditions depend on filling this knowledge gap.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The soil samples were taken from the research field at Murray State University's West Farm (36°36'56.4"N 88°20'56.2" W) in Murray, Kentucky. The Soil Science Laboratory (Room S-403) at Murray State University was the site of the lab experiment. Soil samples were collected from field plots representing two distinct cropping systems: non-leguminous (sunflower and maize) and leguminous (pea and soybean).

4.1 Study site

Figure 1: Map of the study site at Murray State University, Kentucky taken from Google Maps

4.2 Sampling design

The study was conducted using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four cropping systems as treatments: soybean, peas, sunflower, and maize. Each treatment was replicated 6 times, yielding a total of 24 sampling units (4 crops × 6 replications). To guarantee representative coverage of field variability, soil samples were gathered at random within each field. Undisturbed soil cores were taken from the surface soil (0–7 cm) at each replication point to analyze bulk density, macroporosity, microporosity, total porosity, soil water holding capacity (SWHC), and soil water at field capacity (SWFC).

4.3 Methodology

- i. Intact soil columns were extracted using a cylindrical soil core sampler. To minimize structural disruption, the sampler was gently driven vertically into the ground using a wooden board and a hammer. To preserve its pore continuity and natural structure, each core was meticulously dug out with a spade. To prevent dirt loss and maintain the core's internal structure during transportation, each core's two ends were wrapped in fabric after extraction and fastened with rubber bands.
- ii. For analysis, the cores were brought to the lab. Samples were positioned upright in a plastic tray filled with two to three inches of water and immersed for seventy-two hours to get complete saturation. Through capillary and gravitational mechanisms, this guaranteed full soil pore saturation.
- iii. After saturation, the cores were taken out and allowed to drain freely in a standard laboratory setting. To collect water retention data corresponding to various drainage phases, sample weights were recorded at 0 hours (immediately after removal from water), 3 hours, and 24 hours. Soil water holding capacity (SWHC) and soil water at field capacity (SWFC) were subsequently determined using these data.
- iv. To calculate oven-dry weight, all samples were dried for 24 hours at 105°C in a lab oven after drainage measurements. The soil samples were completely dried in an oven, which also enabled accurate bulk density calculation. Additionally, soil water parameters and macro-, micro-, and total porosity were computed from oven-dry weight data.

Laboratory Analysis and calculation

i. Bulk density

To measure soil compaction and its impact on porosity and water flow, bulk density was calculated using the core technique. Each soil core was weighed to determine the oven-dry mass after a 24-hour drying at 105°C. The ratio of oven-dry soil mass to total core volume was used to compute bulk density. The conventional cylindrical volume equation was used to calculate each core's volume and interior dimensions depending on its height and radius:

$$\text{Volume } (V) = \pi r^2 h \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

V = volume of the core (cm³)

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r = internal radius of the core (cm)

h = height of the core (cm)

Now,

Bulk density was then calculated as:

$$\text{Bulk Density (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Oven dried soil weight (g)}}{\text{Core volume (cm}^3\text{)}} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

ii. Total porosity

The standard equation was used to compute total porosity using bulk density and the expected particle density of mineral soils (2.65 g cm⁻³).

The entire pore volume of the soil sample is reflected in this computation.

$$\text{Total porosity (\%)} = 1 - \left(\frac{\text{Bulk density}}{\text{Particle density}} \right) \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where,

Particle density = 2.65 g cm⁻³

iii. Macropores

The part of soil pores that facilitates quick drainage and aeration is known as macroporosity. The difference between soil water content at saturation and that retained after 3 hours of free drainage was used to determine macroporosity. Water drained from macropores was thought to correspond to the volume lost between saturation and 3 hours. The following formula was used to determine macroporosity:

$$\text{Macroporosity} = \left(\frac{\text{Weight of soil after 3 hour drain} - \text{weight of oven-dried soil}}{\text{Weight of oven-dried soil}} \right) \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where,

Weight of oven-dried (OD) soil = (weight of OD soil + weight of cloth + weight of rubber band + soil core) - (weight of cloth + rubber band) - (weight of soil core)

Weight of soil after 3-hour drain = (weight of soil after 3 hours) - (weight of cloth + Rubber band) - (weight of soil core)

iv. Microporosity

Macroporosity was subtracted from total porosity to determine microporosity. According to this method, micropores are the portion of the pore space that is not used for free drainage and is thought to hold water available to plants. This computation is based on the assumption that micropores retain water against gravity, whereas macropores primarily contribute to gravitational water flow.

Micropore (%) = Total porosity (%) - Macroporosity (%)

v. Soil Water Holding Capacity (SWHC)

The total water content held by the soil at saturation in relation to oven-dry weight was used to calculate the soil's water holding capacity:

$$\text{Soil water holding capacity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of soil after saturation} - \text{Weight of OD soil}}{\text{Weight of OD soil}} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where,

Weight of soil after saturation = (weight of soil after 3 hours) - (weight of cloth + Rubber band) - (weight of soil core)

Weight of oven-dried (OD) soil = (weight of OD soil + weight of cloth + weight of rubber band + soil core) - (weight of cloth + rubber band) - (weight of soil core)

vi. Soil Water Field Capacity (SWFC)

The amount of water remaining after a 24-hour drainage period was used to estimate soil water at field capacity. This is an estimate of the amount of water that plants may still access following gravity drainage.

$$\text{Soil water field capacity (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{weight of soil after 24 hour} - \text{weight of OD soil}}{\text{weight of OD soil}} \right) \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

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3. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA), which is appropriate for a completely randomized design. Treatment means were compared using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at $\alpha = 0.05$. The coefficient of variation (CV) was calculated to assess experimental precision. All statistical analyses were performed using appropriate statistical software.

4. RESULTS

6.1 Soil Water Retention Characteristics Under Different Cropping Systems

Soil water retention parameters, including soil water holding capacity (SWHC), soil water field capacity (SWFC), and bulk density, varied among the four cropping systems (Table 1). Sunflower exhibited the highest SWHC (29.13%), followed closely by maize (28.94%) and soybean (28.06%), while peas showed the lowest value (25.29%). Similarly, sunflowers showed the highest SWFC (24.32%), whereas peas showed the lowest (19.92%). Soybean and maize showed intermediate SWFC values of 22.26% each. Despite these numerical differences, statistical analysis revealed no significant differences among treatments for SWHC ($P = 0.327$), SWFC ($P = 0.226$), or bulk density ($P = 0.239$).

Bulk density values ranged from 1.66 g cm⁻³ in maize to 1.73 g cm⁻³ in peas. Leguminous crops (soybean: 1.72 g cm⁻³; peas: 1.73 g cm⁻³) exhibited slightly higher bulk density compared to non-leguminous crops (sunflower: 1.69 g cm⁻³; maize: 1.66 g cm⁻³). The Grand Mean for SWHC, SWFC, and bulk density across all treatments were 27.86%, 22.53%, and 1.704 g cm⁻³, respectively. The coefficients of variation were 14.06% for SWHC, 16.75% for SWFC, and 3.71% for bulk density, indicating acceptable experimental precision.

Table 1: Soil water retention characteristics and bulk density under leguminous and non-leguminous cropping systems

Treatments	Soil Water Holding Capacity (%)	Soil Water Field Capacity (%)	Bulk density (cm ⁻³)
Soybean	28.06 ^a	22.26 ^a	1.72 ^a
Peas	25.29 ^a	19.92 ^a	1.73 ^a
Sunflower	29.13 ^a	24.32 ^a	1.69 ^a
Maize	28.94 ^a	22.26 ^a	1.66 ^a
Grand mean	27.86	22.53	1.704
CV (%)	14.058	16.753	3.712
LSD	4.71	4.546	0.0761
P-value	0.327	0.226	0.239

6.2 Soil Porosity

Characteristics Under Different Cropping Systems

Soil porosity parameters, including macroporosity, microporosity, and total porosity, showed variation across the four cropping systems (Table 2). Sunflower recorded the highest macroporosity (28.05%), followed by maize (27.47%) and soybean (27.08%), while peas exhibited the lowest macroporosity (24.22%). In contrast, peas demonstrated the highest microporosity (10.34%), followed by maize (9.85%), sunflower (8.06%), and soybean (7.83%). Total porosity was highest in maize (37.23%) and sunflower (36.12%), while leguminous crops showed lower values (soybean: 34.91%; peas: 34.57%). However, statistical analysis indicated no significant differences among treatments for macroporosity ($P = 0.328$), microporosity ($P = 0.677$), or total porosity ($P = 0.239$). The grand mean values for macroporosity, microporosity, and total porosity across all treatments were 27.61%, 9.03%, and 35.71%, respectively. The coefficients of variation were 13.69% for macroporosity, 47.86% for microporosity, and 6.75% for total porosity. The relatively high CV for microporosity suggests greater variability in this parameter compared to other porosity measurements.

Table 2: Soil porosity characteristics under leguminous and non-leguminous cropping systems

Treatments	Macropores (%)	Micropore (%)	Total Porosity (%)
Soybean	27.08 ^a	7.83 ^a	34.91 ^a
Peas	24.22 ^a	10.34 ^a	34.57 ^a
Sunflower	28.05 ^a	8.06 ^a	36.12 ^a
Maize	27.47 ^a	9.85 ^a	37.23 ^a
Grand mean	27.61	9.03	35.71
CV (%)	13.685	47.86	6.749
LSD	4.55	5.204	2.9
P-value	0.328	0.677	0.239

DISCUSSION

The results demonstrated that non-leguminous crops, particularly sunflower and maize, exhibited numerically higher soil water-holding capacity (SWHC) and soil water field capacity (SWFC) than leguminous crops, although these differences were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). Sunflowers achieved the highest SWHC (29.13%) and SWFC (24.32%), while peas recorded the lowest values (25.29% and 19.92%, respectively). This pattern can be attributed to several interrelated mechanisms. First, sunflowers and maize possess extensive and deep root systems that create preferential flow pathways and enhance soil aggregation through continuous root turnover and exudate deposition. The fibrous root architecture of maize and the taproot system of sunflower promote the formation of stable macropores that facilitate water infiltration while simultaneously creating micropore networks within aggregates that retain plant-available water (Jarvis, 2020; Bronick and Lal, 2005). Second, non-leguminous crops typically produce greater above- and belowground biomass than the leguminous species tested in this study, leading to higher organic matter inputs that improve soil structure and water retention capacity (Liang et al., 2010; Neves et al., 2022). Third, the root exudates from sunflower and maize contain polysaccharides and other organic compounds that act as binding agents, thereby promoting aggregate stability and creating a more favorable pore-size distribution for water storage.

Conversely, the lower SWHC and SWFC observed in peas may be explained by their relatively shallow root systems and lower biomass production, which limit their capacity to modify soil physical properties during the short growing season (Ngangom et al., 2017; Meena, 2017). Additionally, peas exhibited the highest bulk density (1.73 g cm^{-3}), suggesting greater soil compaction that restricts pore space development and reduces water infiltration and retention. (Håkansson and Lipiec, 2000). The inverse relationship between bulk density and water retention observed in this study is consistent with established soil physics principles, which state that increased soil compaction reduces total porosity and limits the volume available for water storage (Lal and Shukla, 2004).

Maize demonstrated the lowest bulk density (1.66 g cm^{-3}), indicating a less compacted soil structure that facilitates greater pore volume and improved water retention capacity. This finding aligns with previous research showing that cereal crops with extensive root systems can alleviate soil compaction through biological tillage effects (Bronick and Lal, 2005). The slightly elevated bulk density in leguminous crops (soybean: 1.72 g cm^{-3} ; peas: 1.73 g cm^{-3}) compared to non-leguminous crops (sunflower: 1.69 g cm^{-3} ; maize: 1.66 g cm^{-3}) suggests that the physical impact of root architecture and biomass production may outweigh the chemical benefits of nitrogen fixation in determining short-term soil structural properties (Jensen et al., 2012).

The porosity analysis revealed important insights into the mechanisms governing water retention in different cropping systems. Sunflower exhibited the highest macroporosity (28.05%), followed by maize (27.47%), while peas showed the lowest macroporosity (24.22%). This pattern directly corresponds to the observed differences in bulk density and water retention capacity. High macroporosity facilitates rapid water infiltration and drainage, preventing waterlogging and maintaining adequate soil aeration for root respiration and microbial activity (Jarvis, 2007). The superior macroporosity in sunflower and maize can be attributed to their vigorous root growth and high biomass production, which create and maintain large pore channels through mechanical action and organic matter decomposition (Brady and Weil 2016; Martín et al., 2017).

Interestingly, peas demonstrated the highest microporosity (10.34%) among all treatments, yet this did not translate into higher SWFC or SWHC. This counterintuitive finding highlights a critical principle in soil hydrology: water retention is governed not by microporosity alone, but by the balance and connectivity of the entire pore size distribution (Kutilek and Nielsen, 2001). While micropores retain water against gravity and constitute the primary reservoir of plant-available water, excessive microporosity without adequate macroporosity can impede water infiltration, leading to poor drainage and limited aeration (Hillel, 2003). In the case of peas, the high microporosity coupled with low macroporosity (24.22%) and high bulk density (1.73 g cm^{-3}) suggests a poorly structured soil with limited pore connectivity, resulting in restricted water movement and reduced overall water retention capacity (Assouline, 2021).

Total porosity followed a similar trend to macroporosity, with maize showing the highest value (37.23%) and peas the lowest (34.57%). The strong correspondence between total porosity and water retention parameters confirms that overall pore volume is a key determinant of soil hydraulic function (Lal and Shukla, 2004). However, the lack of statistical significance ($P = 0.239$) indicates that within-treatment variability was substantial, possibly due to spatial heterogeneity in soil properties, differences in root distribution patterns, or variations in organic matter content across sampling locations (Herawati et al., 2021).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a comprehensive comparative assessment of soil water retention and porosity characteristics under leguminous (soybean and peas) and non-leguminous (sunflower and maize) cropping systems. The results revealed consistent numerical trends indicating that non-leguminous crops, particularly sunflower and maize, exhibited superior soil physical properties compared to leguminous crops, although these differences were not statistically significant at the $P \leq 0.05$ level. Sunflower demonstrated the highest soil water holding capacity (29.13%) and soil water field capacity (24.32%), while maize showed the lowest bulk density (1.66 g cm^{-3}) and highest total porosity (37.23%). In contrast, peas exhibited the poorest performance across most parameters, with

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the lowest SWHC (25.29%), SWFC (19.92%), macroporosity (24.22%), and total porosity (34.57%), coupled with the highest bulk density (1.73 g cm⁻³).

A key finding of this study is that high microporosity alone does not guarantee improved water retention. Despite peas showing the highest microporosity (10.34%), this did not translate into enhanced SWFC or SWHC, demonstrating that effective water retention requires a balanced pore size distribution with adequate macroporosity to facilitate infiltration and drainage, combined with sufficient microporosity to store plant-available water. The inverse relationship between bulk density and water retention parameters observed across all treatments underscores the critical importance of maintaining low soil compaction to optimize soil hydraulic function.

The superior performance of non-leguminous crops in this study can be attributed to their extensive root systems, higher biomass production, and greater capacity to modify soil physical structure through biological processes. These findings suggest that strategically incorporating non-leguminous crops, particularly sunflower and maize, into crop rotations may enhance soil water retention capacity and improve soil physical resilience, which is increasingly important in the context of climate change and water scarcity. However, the well-documented benefits of legumes for nitrogen fixation and long-term soil fertility should not be overlooked. An integrated cropping system approach that combines both leguminous and non-leguminous species in diversified rotations may provide the optimal strategy for simultaneously improving soil physical structure, water retention, nutrient cycling, and overall soil health.

Future research should focus on long-term field experiments that evaluate the cumulative effects of repeated cropping cycles on soil physical properties across diverse soil types and climatic conditions. Studies should incorporate measurements of infiltration rate, hydraulic conductivity, aggregate stability, organic matter dynamics, root architecture, and microbial activity to elucidate the mechanisms through which different crops influence soil structure and water retention. Additionally, research should investigate the interactive effects of crop rotation sequences, tillage practices, cover cropping, and organic amendments on soil hydraulic properties to develop evidence-based management recommendations for sustainable agricultural systems. Modeling approaches that integrate soil physical processes, hydrological dynamics, and crop growth responses will be valuable for predicting long-term impacts of different cropping systems on soil water availability and crop productivity under future climate scenarios. Such comprehensive research efforts will contribute to the development of climate-resilient cropping systems that optimize soil water use efficiency, enhance agricultural sustainability, and ensure food security amid increasing environmental challenges.

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